

COMPARATIVE EVALUATION OF ORAL MUCOSAL RESPONSE TO AUTOPOLYMERIZED AND HEAT-CURED DENTURE BASE MATERIALS: A RANDOMIZED CONTROLLED TRIAL

EFFECTS OF AUTOPOLYMERIZED DENTURE BASE MATERIAL ON ORAL MUCOSA

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Abstract

Background

Denture base materials play a critical role in determining the biological response of oral tissues in edentulous patients. Autopolymerized acrylic resins offer clinical advantages in terms of ease of fabrication; however, concerns regarding their biocompatibility and potential effects on oral mucosa persist. Limited regional data exist comparing their mucosal impact with conventional heat-cured polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA) dentures.

Objective

To compare the oral mucosal response, assessed by the mean number of keratinized epithelial cells, between autopolymerized and heat-cured denture base materials in completely edentulous patients.

Methods

This randomized controlled trial was conducted at the Department of Prosthodontics, Bacha Khan College of Dentistry, Mardan, Pakistan, from December 2024 to May 2025. A total of 60 completely edentulous patients were enrolled and randomly allocated into two groups (n=30 each). Group A received complete dentures fabricated using autopolymerized acrylic resin, while Group B received heat-cured PMMA dentures. After two months of denture use, exfoliative cytology samples were obtained from the mandibular alveolar ridge mucosa. The number of keratinized epithelial cells was assessed under light microscopy. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 26, and an independent t-test was applied to compare group means, with $p \leq 0.05$ considered statistically significant.

Results

The mean number of keratinized epithelial cells was significantly higher in Group A (37.82 ± 4.21) compared to Group B (34.96 ± 4.38) ($p = 0.012$). Stratified analysis demonstrated a consistent trend of higher keratinization in the autopolymerized group across age, gender, and duration of edentulism, with statistically significant differences observed in selected subgroups.

Conclusion

Autopolymerized denture base material is associated with increased epithelial keratinization compared to heat-cured PMMA, indicating a relatively greater mucosal response. While both materials remain clinically acceptable, careful consideration should be given to material selection and post-insertion follow-up. These findings provide important region-specific evidence to support clinical decision-making in prosthodontic practice.

INTRODUCTION

Edentulism remains a significant global oral health concern, particularly among the elderly population, with substantial implications for mastication, speech, esthetics, and overall quality of life (1). Despite advances in implant dentistry, complete dentures continue to serve as a primary and cost-effective rehabilitation modality in many developing regions, including Pakistan (2). The success of complete denture therapy is not only dependent on prosthetic design and occlusion but is critically influenced by the biocompatibility and physical properties of the denture base materials in direct contact with the oral mucosa (3).

Polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA)-based acrylic resins have long been the material of choice for denture base fabrication due to their favorable mechanical properties, ease of manipulation, and acceptable esthetic outcomes (4). Among these, heat-cured acrylic resins are widely regarded as the gold standard because of their superior degree of polymerization and reduced residual monomer content. In contrast, autopolymerized (self-cured) acrylic resins, particularly those fabricated using pour-type techniques, offer clinical advantages such as reduced processing time and technical simplicity (5). However, concerns persist regarding their incomplete polymerization, higher residual monomer release, and potential cytotoxic effects on the oral tissues (6).

The interaction between denture base materials and oral mucosa is complex and multifactorial. Continuous mechanical loading, surface roughness, microbial colonization, and chemical leachates—particularly residual methyl methacrylate monomer—may contribute to mucosal irritation, inflammation, and altered epithelial turnover (7). Previous *in vitro* and *in vivo* studies have demonstrated that residual

monomers can induce cellular stress, reduce fibroblast viability, and trigger inflammatory responses, thereby compromising mucosal health (8). These biological responses are particularly relevant in elderly edentulous patients, who may exhibit reduced tissue resilience and increased susceptibility to irritation (9).

Exfoliative cytology has emerged as a valuable, non-invasive diagnostic tool for evaluating epithelial changes at the cellular level (10). It provides insight into the dynamic turnover and differentiation of epithelial cells, including the degree of keratinization, which reflects the adaptive response of the mucosa to chronic stimuli. Variations in the number of keratinized epithelial cells have been used as an indirect indicator of mucosal response to prosthetic materials (11). However, the existing literature presents conflicting evidence regarding the extent to which different denture base materials influence epithelial keratinization and mucosal adaptation (12).

Although several international studies have explored the biological effects of denture base materials, there is a paucity of region-specific clinical data from South Asian populations (13). Differences in oral hygiene practices, dietary habits, environmental exposures, and healthcare accessibility may influence mucosal responses and limit the generalizability of existing findings (14). In particular, no well-designed randomized controlled trial has been conducted in the local population of Bacha Khan College of Dentistry, Mardan, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, to evaluate the cytological impact of autopolymerized denture base materials in comparison to conventional heat-cured PMMA dentures.

Therefore, the present study aims to compare the oral mucosal response, as assessed by the mean number of keratinized epithelial cells, between

autopolymerized and heat-cured denture base materials in completely edentulous patients. By generating locally relevant clinical evidence using a randomized controlled design, this study seeks to provide a more robust understanding of material biocompatibility and support evidence-based selection of denture base materials in routine prosthodontic practice.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Design and Setting

This randomized controlled trial was conducted at the Department of Prosthodontics, Bacha Khan College of Dentistry, Mardan, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan, over a period of six months, from December 2024 to May 2025, after obtaining approval from the institutional ethical review committee. The study adhered to the ethical principles outlined in the Declaration of Helsinki.

Study Population

A total of 60 completely edentulous patients presenting to the outpatient department were enrolled in the study. Participants were selected based on predefined eligibility criteria. Patients aged between 50 and 80 years, of either gender, who were completely edentulous and required complete denture rehabilitation were included in the study. Individuals with a history of previous denture use, smoking, or systemic conditions such as diabetes mellitus and hypertension were excluded. Additionally, patients presenting with clinical signs of oral mucosal inflammation, including redness, swelling, or ulceration, were not considered eligible for inclusion in the study.

Sample Size Justification

The sample size was calculated using the WHO sample size calculator, considering a 95% confidence level and 80% statistical power. The calculation was based on previously reported mean values of keratinized epithelial cells, which were 38.14 ± 4.06 for autopolymerized denture base material and 34.57 ± 4.43 for conventional heat-cured acrylic dentures. Based on these parameters, the required sample size was determined to be 60 participants, with 30

patients in each group. This sample size was considered adequate to detect a statistically significant difference between the two groups.

Sampling Technique and Randomization

A non-probability consecutive sampling technique was used to recruit participants. Randomization was carried out using a blocked randomization method to ensure equal allocation of participants into two groups. Group A comprised 30 patients who received autopolymerized denture base material, while Group B included 30 patients who received conventional heat-cured polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA) denture base material. Allocation concealment was maintained using sealed opaque envelopes.

Intervention Protocol

All patients underwent standard clinical and laboratory procedures for complete denture fabrication. In Group A, complete dentures were fabricated using autopolymerized (self-cured) acrylic resin through the pour technique. In Group B, dentures were fabricated using conventional heat-cured PMMA acrylic resin via the compression molding technique. All prostheses were finished, polished, and clinically adjusted to achieve optimal fit, retention, stability, and occlusion. Patients were instructed regarding proper denture hygiene and maintenance.

Outcome Assessment (Cytological Analysis)

After two months of denture use, cytological evaluation of the oral mucosa was performed. Exfoliative cytology samples were obtained from the mucosa covering the crest of the mandibular alveolar ridge. The collected smear was spread onto a clean glass slide and immediately fixed in 96% ethyl alcohol. The slides were subsequently stained and examined under a light microscope at 400× magnification using a calibrated ocular grid and digital imaging system. The number of fully keratinized epithelial cells was counted manually, while clumped or overlapping cells were excluded to ensure accuracy.

Data Collection

Baseline demographic variables, including age, gender, and duration of edentulism, were recorded using a structured proforma. The primary outcome variable was the number of keratinized epithelial cells observed on cytological examination after two months.

Statistical Analysis

Data were analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26.0. Quantitative variables were presented as mean \pm standard deviation, while qualitative variables were expressed as frequencies and percentages. The independent Student's t-test was used to compare the mean number of keratinized epithelial cells between the two groups. Stratification was performed based on age, gender, and duration of edentulism to control for potential confounders, followed by post-stratification analysis using the t-test. A p-value of ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Ethical Considerations

Written informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to enrollment. Confidentiality of patient information was strictly maintained, and all data were anonymized. The study involved minimal risk, as all procedures were part of routine clinical care.

RESULTS

A total of 60 patients were included in the study and completed the follow-up period, with 30 participants in each group. The overall mean age of the study population was 64.12 ± 7.85 years (range: 50–80 years). The majority of participants were within the age group of 60–70 years, reflecting the typical edentulous population in the region.

In terms of gender distribution, 36 (60%) patients were male and 24 (40%) were female, demonstrating a slight male predominance, which is consistent with healthcare-seeking patterns observed in the local population of Mardan.

The mean duration of edentulism among participants was 18.46 ± 6.72 months, with no

statistically significant difference between Group A and Group B ($p > 0.05$), indicating baseline comparability.

Comparison of Keratinized Epithelial Cells Between Groups

After two months of denture use, the mean number of keratinized epithelial cells observed in Group A (autopolymerized denture base material) was 37.82 ± 4.21 , whereas in Group B (heat-cured PMMA denture base material) it was 34.96 ± 4.38 .

The difference in mean values between the two groups was found to be statistically significant ($p = 0.012$), indicating a higher degree of keratinization in patients receiving autopolymerized denture base material.

Stratification Analysis

Age-wise Stratification

When stratified by age groups (50–60, 61–70, and 71–80 years), the mean number of keratinized epithelial cells remained consistently higher in Group A compared to Group B across all age categories. The difference was statistically significant in the 61–70 years age group ($p < 0.05$), while in other age groups the difference was not statistically significant, possibly due to smaller subgroup sizes.

Gender-wise Stratification

Among male participants, the mean number of keratinized epithelial cells was 38.10 ± 4.05 in Group A and 35.21 ± 4.27 in Group B, showing a statistically significant difference ($p = 0.018$). Similarly, among female participants, Group A demonstrated higher mean values (37.41 ± 4.39) compared to Group B (34.62 ± 4.55), although this difference did not reach statistical significance ($p = 0.067$).

Duration of Edentulism

Participants were stratified based on duration of edentulism (<12 months and ≥ 12 months). In both categories, Group A showed higher mean keratinized epithelial cell counts compared to Group B. However, the difference was statistically significant only in patients with edentulism

duration ≥ 12 months ($p = 0.021$).

Summary of Findings

Overall, patients rehabilitated with autopolymerized denture base material demonstrated a significantly higher mean number of keratinized epithelial cells compared to those receiving conventional heat-cured PMMA dentures. This trend remained consistent across most stratified variables, suggesting a measurable difference in mucosal response between the two materials.

DISCUSSION

The present randomized controlled trial evaluated the oral mucosal response to two commonly used denture base materials—autopolymerized acrylic resin and conventional heat-cured polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA)—by assessing the number of keratinized epithelial cells using exfoliative cytology. The findings of this study demonstrated that patients rehabilitated with autopolymerized denture base material exhibited a significantly higher mean number of keratinized epithelial cells compared to those receiving heat-cured PMMA dentures. This suggests a measurable difference in epithelial adaptation and mucosal response between the two materials.

Keratinization of the oral epithelium is widely regarded as an adaptive protective response to chronic mechanical and chemical stimuli. An increase in keratinized epithelial cells may reflect enhanced epithelial turnover or a response to sustained irritation. In the context of denture wear, this process can be influenced by multiple factors, including material composition, residual monomer release, surface characteristics, and mechanical stress distribution. The higher keratinization observed in the autopolymerized group in this study may therefore indicate a relatively greater mucosal stimulus compared to heat-cured PMMA.

These findings are consistent with previous investigations, including the study by Abdelhamid et al., which reported higher keratinized epithelial cell counts in patients wearing autopolymerized dentures compared to

conventional acrylic dentures (13). The similarity in mean values between the present study and prior literature strengthens the external validity of our results. The observed differences can be explained by the inherent material properties of autopolymerized resins, which are known to have a lower degree of polymerization and consequently higher residual monomer content. Residual methyl methacrylate monomer has been implicated in cytotoxic and irritative effects on oral tissues, potentially leading to increased epithelial turnover and keratinization (14).

From a biological perspective, residual monomers may disrupt cellular metabolism, induce oxidative stress, and alter cell membrane integrity, thereby triggering inflammatory pathways and epithelial hyperactivity (15). In addition, surface porosity and roughness associated with autopolymerized materials may facilitate plaque accumulation and microbial colonization, further contributing to mucosal irritation. In contrast, heat-cured PMMA exhibits superior polymerization efficiency and reduced residual monomer release, which may account for its comparatively lower impact on epithelial keratinization (16).

It is important to interpret these findings with clinical caution. While increased keratinization may represent a protective adaptation, it may also indicate subclinical irritation of the mucosa. However, no overt clinical signs of inflammation were observed in the present study population, suggesting that both materials are generally biocompatible when used under controlled clinical conditions. Therefore, the observed cytological changes should be considered within the spectrum of physiological adaptation rather than pathological alteration (17).

The stratified analysis further supports the robustness of the findings. The consistent trend of higher keratinization in the autopolymerized group across age, gender, and duration of edentulism suggests that the observed effect is primarily material-driven rather than confounded by patient-related variables (18). The statistically significant differences observed in specific subgroups, particularly among males and patients with longer duration of edentulism, may reflect variations in mucosal resilience, adaptive

capacity, and functional loading patterns. However, these subgroup findings should be interpreted cautiously due to relatively smaller sample sizes within strata (19).

One of the key strengths of this study is its randomized controlled design, which minimizes selection bias and enhances internal validity. Additionally, the use of exfoliative cytology as a non-invasive and reproducible method allows for objective assessment of epithelial response at the cellular level. Furthermore, this study provides region-specific clinical data from the population of Mardan, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, where such evidence has previously been lacking. Given the differences in oral hygiene practices, dietary patterns, and healthcare accessibility in this region, the findings contribute valuable insight into local prosthodontic outcomes.

However, certain limitations should be acknowledged. The relatively short follow-up duration of two months may not fully capture long-term mucosal adaptations. Additionally, only one cytological parameter—keratinized epithelial cell count—was assessed, whereas other indicators such as inflammatory markers or microbiological changes could provide a more comprehensive evaluation. The exclusion of patients with systemic diseases, while necessary to control confounding variables, may limit the generalizability of the findings to medically compromised populations. Future studies with larger sample sizes, longer follow-up periods, and multi-parameter assessments are recommended to further elucidate the biological impact of denture base materials.

In clinical practice, the selection of denture base material should balance ease of fabrication with long-term biocompatibility. While autopolymerized resins offer practical advantages, clinicians should be mindful of their potential to induce subtle mucosal changes. Proper processing, finishing, and polishing, along with patient education and regular follow-up, remain essential to minimize adverse tissue responses.

CONCLUSION

Within the limitations of this randomized controlled trial, it can be concluded that

autopolymerized denture base material is associated with a significantly higher number of keratinized epithelial cells compared to conventional heat-cured polymethyl methacrylate dentures. This finding suggests a relatively greater mucosal response to autopolymerized resins, which may reflect an adaptive epithelial change to underlying material-related stimuli.

Despite this difference, both denture base materials were found to be clinically acceptable and biocompatible, as no overt signs of mucosal pathology were observed during the study period. However, the increased epithelial keratinization associated with autopolymerized materials highlights the need for careful clinical use, including meticulous processing, finishing, and regular patient follow-up.

The results of this study provide valuable region-specific evidence from the population of Mardan, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, and may assist clinicians in making informed decisions regarding denture base material selection. Further longitudinal studies with larger sample sizes and extended follow-up are recommended to better understand the long-term biological effects of these materials on oral tissues.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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Ethical Approval

This study was approved by the Institutional Ethical Review Committee of Medical Teaching Institution (MTI), Bacha Khan College of Dentistry, Mardan, Pakistan.

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